

Impact of frame-based representations for event-based data in the field of gesture recognition

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Abstract—Gesture recognition using event-based data represents a promising direction in neuromorphic computing, leveraging the asynchronous nature of dynamic vision sensors (DVS) to overcome limitations of traditional frame-based video processing. However, before developing fully spiking solutions, we aim to understand what is the most appropriate use that can be done of event-spike data in presence of a basic convolutional architecture. This work provides insights on the behavior of different conversion methods such as aggregating frames (*time-window*, *spike-count*, *n-bis*), binary representation or time surfaces. These representations are challenged on accuracy metrics in the framework of gesture recognition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gesture recognition systems mainly rely on frame-based video inputs. These systems struggle with high latency, motion blur, and inefficient data processing [1]. Event-based sensors offer an alternative to traditional frame-based cameras by recording only the changes in light intensity at the pixel level, which are then transmitted asynchronously to the systems [2]. Researching the optimal way to interpret event-based data with conventional learning methods could be impactful.

II. CONVERSION METHODS / REPRESENTATIONS

To feed event-based video data into conventional computer vision architectures, it is required to convert them into a frame-like format [3]. In this work we explore five methods: three based on various aggregation criteria, one on binary representations and one on timesurfaces.

III. MODEL

To evaluate the different representations of the event-based data from the datasets against each other, we designed a custom 3-layer 3D convolutional neural network. We used the DVS128 Gesture dataset to train the model.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Two types of experiments were carried out: a) successively training the model with train data sizes ranging from 10% to 90% of the dataset, b) and training the model with 90% of the dataset, and 10% being used for validation.

We can observe that the representations without a fixed frame count (*spike_count*, *time_window*, *timesurface*) performed generally better than those with a fixed frame count (*n_bins*, *binary*), see Figures (a) and (b). Although the accuracy gains

correlate with the increase of the training data size, the difference in performance between the two groups is noticeable especially when training with smaller amounts of data.

We’ve managed to achieve the best overall accuracy of 89% with the *time_window* representation and a batch size of 16. With a batch size of 8, we achieved 88% accuracy with both the *time_window* and *timesurface* representations.

(a) Test accuracy evolution with batch size of 16

(b) Boxplot with test accuracies with batch size of 16

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Amir, B. Taba, D. Berg, T. Melano, J. McKinstry, C. Di Nolfo, T. Nayak, A. Andreopoulos, G. Garreau, M. Mendoza, *et al.*, “A low power, fully event-based gesture recognition system,” in *CVPR, 2017*.
- [2] U. Mallik, M. Clapp, E. Choi, G. Cauwenberghs, and R. Etienne-Cummings, “Temporal change threshold detection imager,” in *ISSCC 2005*.
- [3] G. Gallego, T. Delbrück, G. Orchard, C. Bartolozzi, B. Taba, A. Censi, S. Leutenegger, A. J. Davison, J. Conradt, K. Daniilidis, and D. Scaramuzza, “Event-based vision: A survey,” *PAMI, 2022*.

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